

Spectrophotometric and Amperometric Studies of Complexes of Dysprosium(III) with Rhodamine B : Analytical Complexometry

O. P. RATHORE and S. C. LAVALE*

Chemical Research Laboratory, Government P. G. College, Betul-460 001

Manuscript received 2 February 1995, revised 28 May 1996, accepted 7 June 1996

Survey of literature reveals that no work seems to have been carried out on spectrophotometric studies of complexes of Dy^{III} with tetraethyldiamino-*o*-carboxylphenyl-xynthenylchloride (Rhodamine B)¹. Two direct complexometric methods for determination of Dy^{III} in pure solution or in presence of other common metal ions are reported in the present communication.

Results and Discussion

The method of Vosburgh and Cooper was used to study the nature of the complex formed². The λ_{\max} for visible spectra of Dy^{III}-rhodamine B complex was found to be 595 nm. The stoichiometry of the complex was determined using Job's method of continuous variation³. The measurement were carried at pH 2.50 \pm 0.01. Stoichiometry of Dy^{III}-rhodamine B complex determined by Job's method of continuous variation³ was found to be 1 : 3, which was confirmed by amperometric titration of Dy^{III} with rhodamine B. Mole-ratio method⁴ also revealed 1 : 3 stoichiometry. The values of α (0.13), K_s (2.47×10^{10}) and hence $\log K_s$ (10.39) alongwith ΔG° ($-14.26 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) were calculated using standard equation for dissociation and Vant' Hoff isotherm. These values support the spectral and amperometric analytical results for the determination of Dy^{III} using rhodamine B.

Amperometric titration for the estimation of Dy^{III} at pH 2.50 \pm 0.01 was carried out following the usual procedure⁵. The minimum amount of Dy^{III} i.e. 5.3 mg could be successfully estimated in presence of various diverse ions. It was observed that a 100-fold concentration of chloride, chlorate, sulphate, nitrate, acetate, Na⁺, K⁺ and Mg^{II} did not interfere. A 20-fold excess of Cu^{II}, Fe^{III}, Ca^{II}, Ba^{II}, carbonate, bromide and thiosulphate could be tolerated. However, a 5-fold excess of Au^{III}, In^{III}, Tl^{III}, Sb^{III}, Cd^{II}, Ga^{III}, W^{VI} and Ag^I could not be tolerated. Rare earths and higher ratio of mixing hampered the titrimetric procedure seriously.

The proposed titration methods of determination for Dy^{III} (photometry and amperometry) are quite selective and sensitive. The results reveal that microgram quantities of Dy^{III} could be estimated.

Experimental

A Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20 spectrophotometer was used. Photometric titration was carried on a Systronic 112 colorimeter at 595 nm. Amperometric titration was carried out using a Elico Cl-25D polarograph with a d.m.e. having capillary characteristics of $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.14 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Current was recorded on an Osaw potential reflecting galvanometer. Titrations were carried out at pH 2.50 \pm 0.01. Dysprosium oxide (Kotch Light) was used to prepare Dy^{III} solution (10^{-3} M) and standardised⁶. Rhodamine B (B.D.H.) solution was prepared in double-distilled water. To know the effect of diverse ions metal ions solutions were prepared. The absorption of Dy^{III} complexes of rhodamine-B was measured in solution to determine metal-to-ligand ratio by Job's method and mole-ratio method.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. S. P. Bhise, Principal, Government Post-Graduate College, Betul, for facilities.

References

1. J. T. STOCK, "Amperometric Titrations", R. E. Krieger Pub Co., Huntington, 1975, S. C. LAVALE and K. S. PITRE, *J. Electrochem Soc. India*, 1981, **30**, 328, H. A. FLASCHKA and A. J. BARNARD, JR, "Chelates in Analytical Chemistry", Metrcel Dekker, New York, 1972, Vol. 4.
2. W. C. VOSBURGH and C. R. COOPER, *J. Am. Chem Soc*, 1941, **63**, 437.
3. P. JOB, *Ann Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
4. D. A. SKOOG, "Principals of Instrumental Analysis", 4th ed., Saunder, New York, 1980.
5. S. C. LAVALE, Ph D. Thesis, Saugar University, 1982
6. S. C. LAVALE and K. S. PITRE, *Rev. Roum Chim.*, 1983, **28**, 52